

Thermodynamic Functions of Diazines and some Substituted Diazines

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Statistical method of calculation of thermodynamic functions, namely, heat capacity (C_p), enthalpy function $(H^0 - E^0)/T$, free energy function $(G^0 - E^0)/T$ and entropy (S^0), is highly reliable as compared to any other physical methods. Direct measurements by experiments of these quantities are usually difficult and sometimes, not even possible.

Vibrational analysis of 4,6-dichloropyrimidine^{1,2}, 2,4,5,6-tetrachloropyrimidine^{2,3}, pyrazine⁴⁻¹⁰, pyridazine-d₀^{6,7,11} and pyridazine-d₄¹¹ has been done by earlier workers. Although the vibrational analysis of these molecules has been studied, the thermodynamic functions of these molecules are not reported. In view of this we decided to compute the thermodynamic functions for these molecules at a pressure of 1 atm in the temperature range 100–1500 K under the rigid rotor-harmonic oscillator approximation and using the fundamental frequencies available in the literature^{1,2,10,11}.

Computation of thermodynamic properties :
The contribution of the vibrational energy to the total energy can be calculated from the vibrational frequencies of the molecule. In the same way, the rotational energy contribution can be calculated from the moment of inertia of the molecule. The spectroscopically measured frequencies and the moment of inertia are important variables in determining the thermodynamic functions of a molecule.

According to Born-Oppenheimer¹² approximation, the total energy of a system is given by

$$E = E_{\text{trans}} + E_{\text{rot}} + E_{\text{vib}} + E_{\text{elec}} \quad (1)$$

where the subscripts trans, rot, vib and elec stand for translational, rotational, vibrational and electronic respectively. The total partition function Q in terms of energy is given by

$$Q = \sum g_i \exp(-E_i/KT) \\ = Q_{\text{trans}} \cdot Q_{\text{rot}} \cdot Q_{\text{vib}} \cdot Q_{\text{elec}} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Variation of enthalpy function with absolute temperature for (O) 4,6-dichloropyrimidine, (●) 2,4,5,6-tetrachloropyrimidine, (□) pyrazine, (Δ) pyridazine-d₀ and (▲) pyridazine-d₄.

where g_i is the statistical weight of the i -th energy level, k the Boltzman constant and T the absolute temperature. The partition function for each type of energy may be evaluated separately from equation (2) and then the corresponding thermodynamic functions are calculated. The contribution of electronic partition function is small and is ignored because E_{elec} is large as compared to kT at ordinary temperatures. The standard expression as given by Colthup *et al.*¹³ are used in the computation of various partition functions and their contribution to different thermodynamic parameters were made on a IBM-PC computer.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of available spectroscopic data of the polyatomic molecules 4,6-dichloropyrimidine, 2,4,5,6-tetrachloropyrimidine, pyrazine, pyridazine- d_0 and pyridazine- d_4 , it is possible to compute statistically their thermodynamic properties with fair degree of accuracy. The molecular structures of 4,6-dichloropyrimidine and 2,4,5,6-tetrachloropyrimidine are taken from related compounds

available in literature^{14,15}. The molecular structure of pyrazine was studied by Wheatly¹⁵ using X-ray techniques. The molecular structure of pyridazine- d_0 and pyridazine- d_4 are taken from related compounds available in literature^{17,18}.

The atomic masses are taken from the literature¹⁹. In the computation of principal moments of inertia I_x , I_y , I_z all the molecules have been considered as planar (x - y plane) in which 4,6-dichloropyrimidine and 2,4,5,6-tetrachloropyrimidine belong to C_{2v} , pyrazine to D_{2h} , pyridazine to C_{2v} point groups respectively. The computed values of the principal moments of inertia are : 4,6-dichloropyrimidine I_x , 97.04×10^{46} kg m²; I_y , 14.01×10^{46} kg m²; I_z , 111.05×10^{46} kg m²; 2,4,5,6-tetrachloropyrimidine I_x , 138.34×10^{46} kg m²; I_y , 96.38×10^{46} kg m²; I_z , 235.66×10^{46} kg m²; pyrazine I_x , 13.51×10^{46} kg m²; I_y , 18.76×10^{46} kg m²; I_z , 32.27×10^{46} kg m²; pyridazine- d_0 I_x , 20.15×10^{46} kg m²; I_y 14.28

Fig. 2. Variation of free energy function with absolute temperature for (O) 4,6-dichloropyrimidine, (●) 2,4,5,6-tetrachloropyrimidine, (□) pyrazine, (Δ) pyridazine- d_0 and (▲) pyridazine- d_4 .

Fig. 3. Variation of enthalpy with absolute temperature for (O) 4,6-dichloropyrimidine, (●) 2,4,5,6-tetrachloropyrimidine, (□) pyrazine, (Δ) pyridazine- d_0 and (▲) pyridazine- d_4 .

Fig. 4. Variation of heat capacity with absolute temperature for (O) 4,6-dichloropyrimidine, (●) 2,4,5,6-tetrachloropyrimidine, (□) pyrazine, (Δ) pyridazine-d₀ and (▲) pyridazine-d₄.

$\times 10^{46} \text{ kg m}^2$, I_z , $34.43 \times 10^{46} \text{ kg m}^2$; pyridazine-d₄ I_x , $20.22 \times 10^{46} \text{ kg m}^2$; I_y , $15.56 \times 10^{46} \text{ kg m}^2$; I_z , $35.78 \times 10^{46} \text{ kg m}^2$.

The computed results²⁰ of the thermodynamic functions, namely, the heat capacity (C_p^0), the enthalpy function ($H^0 - E_0^0$)/ T , the free energy function ($G^0 - E_0^0$)/ T and entropy (S^0) for the above five compounds are represented by curves in Figs. 1–4 at various temperatures ranging from 100 to 1500 K. The thermodynamic functions rise more rapidly in the low temperature range than less rapidly in the high temperature range. The trend of variation with temperature is similar to those reported in literature^{21–25}.

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